

ELECTRICAL AND THERMAL CONDUCTIVITIES OF AU NANOPARTICLE DECORATED GRAPHENE NANOPATELET 'PAPER'

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1 Introduction

Numerous research efforts are underway directed at discovering the superior and unique properties of single layer graphene and multilayer graphene nanoplatelets. Typical methods to synthesize metal nanoparticle on graphene surface involve covalent functionalization of graphene surface to induce anchoring sites for the metal precursor and subsequent attachment of the reduced nanoparticles to the surface [1]. This approach results in the disruption of the sp² bonded carbon atoms in the basal plane which leads to reduced transport properties of the graphene because of additional scattering sites. Another widely adopted technique involves nanoparticle growth on non-covalently functionalized graphene surfaces, which preserves the intrinsic properties of graphene nanosheets thanks to the minimum chemical perturbation of the basal planes. Other techniques of metal nanoparticle decoration on graphitic nanostructure include electrodeposition, evaporation, solventless bulk synthesis and etc. While these methods have some processing advantages over solution-phase techniques, they are usually quite expensive and energy intensive.

Despite the many publications on superior electrochemical properties of nanoparticle/graphene hybrid, none discusses the transport properties of this hybrid material when made into a 'paper-like' structure where the nanoparticles are located at the surfaces and interfaces of the graphene nanosheets. In this work, we reported a fast, one-pot synthesis of gold nanoparticle decorated graphene nanoplatelets (GNP) in the presence of a polyethyleneimine (PEI) matrix with microwave assisted heating [2]. GNPs are few layer graphene nanosheets produced from microwave exfoliation of graphite intercalated compounds followed by a combination of size

reduction processes. Research conducted in MSU has led to a process that can produce exfoliated graphene nanoplatelets with controlled thicknesses ranging from 1-10 nm and platelet diameters from 100 to 10000 nm [3]. Polyethyleneimine, a hydrophilic polymer with primary, secondary and tertiary amino groups and a positive charge in the neutral aqueous solution, adsorbs onto the highly hydrophobic GNP surface and stabilizes the GNP particles in water. In addition, PEI contains one of the highest densities of amino groups among all polymers, donating electrons that help reduce metal ions [4]. Au/GNP particles were then dispersed in water and made into a 'paper' by vacuum assisted self assembly. The electrical and thermal conductivity of the Au/GNP paper were characterized. It is believed adsorbed PEI is likely to interfere with both electron and phonon transport within the hybrid paper. Therefore, a thermal annealing at 340°C was applied to remove the PEI within the paper by thermal decomposition. Since the GNP is highly oxidation resistant to temperatures greater than 500°C, chemical changes in the GNP did not take place during annealing. It is also worth noting that the hybrid paper sample as prepared by self-assembly is highly porous. In order to reduce porosity and enhance particle alignment in the paper, the annealed samples were compacted in a hydraulic press at room temperature. The impact of gold nanoparticles on both electron and phonon transport in this hybrid paper under different experimental conditions (thermal annealing, cold compaction) is discussed.

2. Results and discussions

At pH <10, the positively charged polymer chain also induces electrostatic repulsion that contributes to good dispersion of the nanoplatelets. As the

tetrachloroauric acid dissolved in water was mixed with the GNP suspensions, the AuCl_4^- ions complex with the positive functional groups of PEI adsorbed on the GNP surface (chloride ligands were replaced by amine groups of PEI). The adsorbed PEI chains, in this case, serve as templates for subsequent Au nanoparticle growth on the surface of GNP. The addition of H^+ ions also lowers the pH of the solution to around 6, inducing more positive charges on the chain of PEI and more electrostatic attraction with AuCl_4^- [5]. The reduction of Au^{3+} to Au^0 was then carried out in a microwave oven where the heating rate is fast enough to cause a rapid temperature increase in the solution due to the high polarity of water molecules, creating a high concentration of radicals which facilitates the electron transfer from the radicals of PEI to the metal precursor. As soon as the solution is supersaturated with metal atoms, Au atoms form nuclei. The critical size of the nucleus as well as nucleation activation energy control the nucleation rate and depend on the surface tension of the nuclei-solvent interface when the radius of nuclei is small. Therefore, a higher surface tension corresponds to a larger critical nucleus size and a lower nucleation rate, which should be avoided in synthesizing monodispersed small nanoparticles. Upon formation of the nucleus, polyethyleneimine, with a lower surface tension than Au atoms, adsorbs on the surface of the metal atoms reducing the nucleation energy barrier and critical nucleus size. As a result, more primary particles with low surface energy are formed leading to generation of smaller secondary particles whose growth and coarsening are also affected by surface tension. Scheme 1 represents the typical procedures and the interactions between the metal ions and the active sites on GNP particles and subsequent formation of nanoparticles on GNP.

Figure 1 shows the SEM images of Au nanoparticle decorated GNP prepared at 0.3wt% and 0.6wt% PEI in the solution. It is found that the size and loading of the Au nanoparticles synthesized by this technique correlated with the concentration of PEI in the solution. The size of the nanoparticles was reduced while the loading increased with higher concentration of PEI in the solution. With a higher concentration of PEI in the solution, the number of nuclei with a lower surface energy increased which leads to formation of more primary and secondary

particles. In addition, more PEI chains would adsorb on to the surface of GNP acting as templates for Au nanoparticle growth. There is no obvious agglomeration of Au nanoparticles on the surface of GNP, which is also believed to be the result of PEI encapsulation that stabilizes the nanoparticles in the solution electrostatically.

Au/GNP paper was prepared by vacuum assisted self assembly. Figure 2 shows the photos of the as-made papers after being removed from the filter membrane. The as-made paper is very flexible and shows certain mechanical robustness under bending. Table 1 shows the apparent densities of the samples at different conditions.

Thermal diffusivity of the samples prepared at different experimental conditions (as-made, annealed, annealed and cold compacted) were measured by Nanoflash 447 (Netzsch Instruments). Given the density of the sample, and the specific heat, which was measured by differential scanning calorimetry, thermal conductivity of the sample can be obtained: $\kappa = \alpha \rho C_p$ where κ is thermal conductivity with a unit of $\text{W/m}^2\text{K}$, α is thermal diffusivity with a unit of mm^2/s , and C_p is specific heat with a unit of $\text{J/g}^\circ\text{K}$.

As shown in Figure 3a, the through-plane thermal conductivity of all the samples followed the same trend with a slight increase after thermal annealing and a reduction after cold compaction. It is believed PEI adsorbed either on the GNP surface or on the Au nanoparticles scatter the phonons in this paper-like structure, contributing to a larger thermal interface resistance which is a major impediment to phonon transport [6, 7]. A thermal annealing treatment removed most of the PEI in the paper, presumably reducing the interfacial resistance as suggested by a 20% improvement in through-plane diffusivity. However, upon annealing and cold compaction, thermal conductivity decreased for all the samples. Compaction of the sample effectively eliminated large pores within the paper created during filtration and the nanoplatelets were more aligned due to the compressive stress. The better orientation of the nanoplatelets reduced the through-plane phonon transport due to the intrinsically low thermal conductivity of GNP with multiple layers of graphene held together with weak Van der Waals forces and the high probability of interface scattering

between individual nanoplatelets. Cold compaction will densify the “loose” porous nanostructure. Despite the fact that macro sized pores collapse upon compaction in neat GNP paper, there are still numerous slit pores inside it that would interfere with the transport of electrons and phonons. With the hybrid paper, Au nanoparticles on the surface of GNP now have a much higher probability of contact with each other, serving as bridging agents or mini columns which might facilitate propagation of phonons within the paper structure. Nonetheless, the experimental results for “annealed and cold compacted” samples indicated a reduction in the through-plane conductivity for the Au/GNP hybrid paper. In this case, a phonon is forced to go through a Au nanoparticle to go from one GNP to another. In particular, the cross sectional area of heat conduction is reduced due to the presence of Au nanoparticles. As a result, the through-plane thermal conductivity of the Au/GNP hybrid sample is lower than the neat GNP paper after annealing and cold compaction.

The in-plane thermal conductivity is shown in Figure 3b. Thermal annealing causes decomposition and removal of PEI from within the sample, improving the “thermal contact area” by reducing interface resistance. A moderate increase of around 10% was observed for samples measured after annealing. Cold-compaction of the samples restores the orientation of the nanoplatelets, making the paper more anisotropic in heat conduction. In particular, the thermal conductivity of all “annealed and cold compacted” samples improve by almost 70% with neat GNP paper approaching as high as 200 W/m²K. It is worth noting that thermal conductivity of the Au/GNP hybrid samples are lower than the neat GNP paper, which is in accord with the trend observed from through-plane measurements. It is believed that those Au nanoparticles are more likely to serve as phonon scatterers than mini heat conduction channels within the hybrid samples.

The self assembly of GNP with and without Au nanoparticles did have an impact on the thermal conductivity of the samples. In particular, the gold nanoparticles that were expected to provide additional heat channels through the plane of the paper structure to improve the heat conduction turned out to be ineffective. To investigate if the

same phenomenon observed in phonon transport also applies to electrons, both the through-plane and in-plane electrical conductivity of these papers were measured and reported in Figure 4a and b.

From Figure 4a, the in-plane electrical conductivity of the papers increased with annealing and cold compaction. The improvement can be explained by the effective decomposition of electrically insulating PEI from the samples through thermal annealing and significant reduction of pore volumes through cold compaction, both contributing to decreasing electron tunneling resistance. In particular, the GNP paper decorated with Au nanoparticles of different size and distribution density showed higher conductivity than the neat GNP paper. Hybrid GNP papers with individual nanoplatelets decorated with smaller and higher coverage of Au nanoparticles exhibited higher in-plane electrical conductivity. Upon cold compaction, the collapse of macro pores in the sample brings more Au nanoparticles into immediate contact, effectively bridging previously isolated nanoplatelets. It is worth noting that the in-plane conductivity reaches a value as high as 1500 S/cm for Au/GNP (0.6wt% PEI) hybrid paper, which is almost 70% higher than the neat GNP paper (880 S/cm) at the same condition. It is worth noting that the in-plane electrical conductivity is measured to be 2×10^4 S/cm for bulk graphite [8], one order of magnitude higher than the value reported here for Au/GNP hybrid sample.

The through-plane electrical resistivity of the papers was measured by a two-point method on the samples that have been annealed and cold compacted. The result is shown in Figure 4b. The results from as-made and annealed samples are not reported because the measured electrical resistance fluctuates a large amount possibly due to the open porous structure inside the sample. The measurements on the annealed and cold compacted samples were stable enough thanks to the dense and compact structure of the paper. The Au nanoparticles effectively bridged adjacent GNPs, creating mini channels for the cross plane electron transport as evidenced by the drop in the through-plane resistivity. It is thus evident that although the through-plane conductivity is small due to a greater anisotropic electronic conduction induced by cold compaction, the Au nanoparticles did facilitate the electron transport within the paper structure, making individual nanoplatelets more

electrically connected. As a comparison, the through-plane resistivity for bulk graphite is 0.1~1 ohm cm, a few orders of magnitude lower than the highly ordered layer structure reported here [8].

3. Conclusion

Gold nanoparticles of a uniform size distribution were successfully synthesized on exfoliated graphene nanoplatelets by microwave assisted heating in a polyethyleneimine/water solution. It is believed that fast super-saturation of metal atoms with low surface tension is desired for producing monodispersed small nanoparticles. A self-standing, mechanically robust Au/GNP nanostructured multilayered ‘paper’ was prepared by vacuum assisted self assembly. Thermal annealing to decompose and remove PEI improves both electrical and thermal conductivities. Paper porosity was significantly reduced by cold compaction which produces closer contact between individual nanoplatelets. Au nanoparticles on the surface of GNP reduce phonon transport by introducing more scattering sites at the interface due to a vast difference in the vibrational density of states for phonons in gold and GNP and by reducing the total cross sectional area for heat conduction. However, the Au nanoparticles act as electron super highways that make nanoplatelets more electrically connected.

Fig. 1a. SEM of Au/GNP prepared at 0.3wt% PEI in water.

Fig. 1b. SEM of Au/GNP prepared at 0.6wt% PEI in water.

Scheme 1: interaction of PEI coated GNP with AuCl_4^-

Fig 2. Photos of the neat GNP and Au/GNP hybrid paper

Table 1: Average densities of GNP and Au/GNP papers at different conditions:

Density (ρ : g/cm ³)	As-made	Annealed	Annealed & cold compacted
GNP paper	0.62	0.62	1.5
Au/GNP (0.3wt% PEI)	0.58	0.57	1.5
Au/GNP (0.6wt% PEI)	0.58	0.58	1.5

Fig 4a: Through-plane electrical resistivity of anneal & cold compacted GNP and Au/GNP paper. **b**: In-plane electrical conductivity of anneal & cold compacted GNP and Au/GNP paper.

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